

**AMERICAN YEARBOOK OF INTERNATIONAL
LAW**

ISSN: 2732-9925

Vol.2, n.1, 2023

Article 7

**Prevention of disasters and obligations imposed by
international environmental law**

Robin Moller

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10680337](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10680337)

Follow this and additional works at:
<https://ayil.rf.gd/index.php/home>

Recommended Citation

Moller, R. (2023). Prevention of disasters and obligations imposed by international environmental law. *American Yearbook of International Law*, vol. 2, n. 1, 267-324, Article 7

Available at: <https://ayil.rf.gd/index.php/home/issue/current>

This article is brought to you for free and open access by CEIJ. It has been accepted for inclusion in American Yearbook of International Law. For more information, please contact: AYIL@usa.com

Prevention of disasters and obligations imposed by international environmental law

[DOI:10.5281/zenodo.10680337](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10680337)

Robin Moller, Post PhD, L. Douglas Wilder School of
Government and Public Affairs, U.S

Abstract: The continuous growth of natural disasters together with climate change are phenomena that require our legal attention. The continuous disasters caused by natural events, as well as the products of human activities of industrial and technological accidents, pollution and continuous environmental degradation are situations where states and international institutions show increasing attention and through regulatory instruments and international environmental standards try to manage the different phases of the cycle of a disaster. The sources of international environmental law that are the cornerstone of the disaster prevention obligation together with the minimum measures that states take to fulfill this obligation are analyzed in various treaties and are part of our investigation together with the interpretation of the jurisprudence which comes from international tribunals, conferences of the parties

and treaty bodies. Within this complex framework and with a lot of data we are here to analyze and give some answers, even of a theoretical nature, of the international protection of natural disasters at a global level.

Keywords: international law; natural disasters; disaster risk reduction; soft law; hard law; international environmental law; international treaties in international environmental law.

Introduction

In the field of disaster risk reduction, soft law acts include risks that are determined by technological and environmental hazards (Peel, Fischer, 2016; Lauta, 2016; Bartolini, 2017; Tladi, 2017; Zorzi Giustiiani, 2018; Aronsson-Storrier, 2019; Sefsaf, 2022)¹. The category of technological hazards includes industrial or technological activities, industrial pollution, the release of toxic

¹See the ASEAN Agreement on Disaster Management and Emergency Response (AADMER), art. 1, par. 5. Tampere Convention on the provision of telecommunication resources for disaster mitigation and relief operations, adopted in Tampere in 1998, entered into force on 8 January 2005, with 48 states parties, art. 1, par. 6. ILC, Draft articles on the protection of persons in the event of disasters with commentaries, 68^o session, UN doc. A/71/10, 2016: https://legal.un.org/ilc/texts/instruments/english/draft_articles/6_3_2016.pdf, art. 3: “(...) 1. Each state shall reduce the risk of disasters by taking appropriate measures, including through legislation and regulations, to prevent, mitigate, and prepare for disasters; 2. Disaster risk reduction measures include the conduct of risk assessments, the collection and dissemination of risk and past loss information, and the installation and operation of early warning systems; (...)”.

waste, nuclear radiation emissions, factory explosions, fires, chemicals, etc². On the other hand, the group of environmental dangers includes those that come from environmental degradation, pollution, soil and water, the loss of biodiversity, rising sea levels, etc³.

Such disastrous risks are part of the matter of disaster prevention and international environmental protection standards. The acts of hard and soft law in the field of disaster risk reduction⁴ as well as the international standards that impose the related obligations to prevent disasters help to determine their content.

In various areas of law, disaster prevention is now a topic of

²UN Secretary General, Report on indicators and terminology relating to Disaster Risk Reduction, 2016, <https://digitallibrary.un.org/record/852089>, p. 19: “(...) “(...) processes or conditions, often development-related, that influence the level of disaster risk by increasing levels of exposure and vulnerability or reducing capacity (...)”.

³Hyogo framework for action 2005-2015: building the resilience of Nations and communities to disasters (Hyogo framework), adopted from the World conference on disaster reduction and from the UNGA, International Strategy for Disaster Reduction, Res. 60/195 of 2 March 2006, par. 1. European Union Regulation 2021/836 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 20 May 2021 amending decision no. 1313/2013/EU on a Union Civil Protection Mechanism, Recital 11, art. 13, par. 3. Sendai framework for disaster risk reduction 2015-2030 (Sendai framework), adopted by the World conference on disaster risk reduction, Sendai, 2015; subsequently adopted by the United Nations General Assembly, UNGA, Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030, Res. 69/283 of 23 June 2015, par. 15. United Nations Secretary-General, Implementation of the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030, UN Doc. A/75/226, 23 July 2020. UN, OIEWG, Report of the open-ended intergovernmental expert working group (OIEWG) on indicators and terminology relating to disaster risk reduction, UN doc. A/71/644, 1 December 2016, which is affirmed that: “(...) disaster risk reduction is aimed at preventing new and reducing existing disaster risk and managing residual risk, all of which contribute to strengthening resilience and therefore to the achievement of sustainable development (...)”.

⁴ILC, Draft articles on the protection of persons in the event of disasters, op. cit., “(...)a calamitous event or series of events resulting in widespread loss of life, great human suffering and distress, mass displacement, or large-scale material or environmental damage, thereby seriously disrupting the functioning of society (...)”.

general culture of internationalists that enters the general framework of the protection of human rights and environmental protection.

The topics of analysis of the groups that include environmental protection in the disaster risk reduction sector justify the distinct preventive obligations, the specific needs of environmental protection and disaster prevention. The obligations concern dangerous industrial activities with a direct way and the prevention of disasters that aim to prevent accidents resulting from serious damage to people, property and the environment and obligations to protect biodiversity as a response to climate change and prevention of physical events that can cause a disaster contribute to the reduction of environmental disasters⁵.

The related obligations imposed by international standards are determined on convergent approaches that emerge from treaties and decisions that are adopted by international courts and tribunals and by other non-judicial bodies for the competence and interpretation of the application of these types of treaties. The disaster prevention obligations enter the due diligence sector where a plurality of acts and institutions require the adoption of a disaster prevention action which highlights a general standard of behavior which requires a state to fulfill the obligation to do everything possible to prevent its disaster.

⁵UNGA, International Strategy for Disaster Reduction, Res. 69/219 of 14 January 2015.

It is an approach that is based on the reasoning that some international courts interpret rules that contain general due diligence obligations (Dzehtsiarou, 2015)⁶ within a framework of various fields of international law that are in continuous and mutual interaction in the field of international protection of natural disasters.

The “environmental disaster” in international law

Speaking of international environmental law we are referring to a global protection of the environment which is codified through treaties on the subject which in reality have not taken into consideration the term disaster⁷. First of all we recall the Declaration of Rio on the environment and development of 1992 which requires the state and the territory to verify the natural disaster as well as to immediately notify the event to the other states that may be affected⁸. The term disaster indicates an emergency situation by the United Nations Environmental Program (UNEP) (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018)⁹ and

⁶ECtHR, *Demir and Baykara v. Turkey* of 12 November 2008, par. 85-86.

⁷Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, adopted in Helsinki on 17 March 1992, entered into force on 19 April 2000, with 41 states parties, art. 2: <https://unece.org/DAM/env/documents/2006/teia/Convention%20E%20no%20annex%20I.pdf>

⁸Declaration of Rio, Principle 18.

⁹UNEP, Further improvement of environmental emergency prevention, preparedness, assessment, response and mitigation, UNEP/GC.22/INF/5, 13 November 2002, par. 3.

by the International Law Commission and the related articles on the prevention of transboundary environmental damage¹⁰. International environmental law considers unforeseeable situations of human or natural origin that cause environmental damage of a serious nature¹¹ as emergencies.

Within this framework there are obligations to prepare the response to any adverse event¹², as well as the notification to the state/states that is in danger¹³ and to individuals who are exposed to risk¹⁴. The concept of disaster refers to hypotheses of environmental damage that characterizes the unpredictability for the severity of the effects that respects those that arise in the states of the damage mitigation obligations.

According to the project on the prevention of transboundary environmental damage, the concept of disaster has been called

¹⁰ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm from hazardous activities, with commentaries, 53^o section, UN Doc. A/56/10, 2001, art. 16, comm. 1.

¹¹Convention on the law of the non-navigational uses of international watercourses, adopted in New York 21 May 1997, entered into force on 17 August 2014, with 37 states parties, art. 28, par. 1. UNEP, Further improvement of environmental emergency prevention, preparedness, assessment, response and mitigation, UNEP/GC.22/INF/5, 13 November 2002, par. 3. ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, cit., art. 17, comm. 3.

¹²ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, cit., art. 16; Convention on the law of the non-navigational uses of international watercourses, adopted in New York on 21 May 1997, entered into force on 17 August 2014, with 37 states parties, art. 28, par. 1, art. 8.

¹³ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, cit., art. 17; Convention on the law of the non-navigational uses of international watercourses, cit., art. 28, par. 2; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, cit., art. 10, par. 2.

¹⁴Aarhus Convention was adopted of 25 June 1998, art. 5, par. 1(c). <https://unece.org/environment-policy/public-participation/aarhus-convention/introduction>

to indicate the seriousness of the damage caused by human activities that are qualified as super dangerous¹⁵, stating that:

“(...) a danger that is rarely expected to materialize but might assume, on that rare occasion, grave (more than significant, serious or substantial) proportions (...) of the risks deriving from the exercise of “ultra-dangerous” activities justifies the obligation to take preventive action despite the low probability that environmental damage materializes (...)”.

This statement complies with the precautionary principle, which is contained in various international treaties and instruments relating to the environment (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018).

The “definition” of the concept of disaster includes the decisions and resolutions of the Conferences of the Parties (or COP) which are established by treaties on environmental matters (Wierserna, 2009). In reality, these are acts that are not binding and recognized with a certain relevance by the authority of the body they come from (Boisson De Chazournes, 2009; Brown, 2021). The COPs have adopted acts by virtue of the powers that adapt the content of the treaties to the relative innovations of a technical and scientific nature. The decisions and resolutions of the COPs consider the interpretation of the treaties and related documents of the conferences of the parties as functions that show control over the implementation of the treaties (Wierserna, 2009)¹⁶. In the most recent acts of the COP, the notion of

¹⁵ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 2, comm. 3.

¹⁶ILC, Second report on subsequent agreements and subsequent practice in relation to the interpretation of treaties, according to the Special Rapporteur A/CN.4/671, 2014, par. 84-111.

disaster is a fact oriented towards recognizing the contribution of legal instruments for the protection of the environment which lead to the reduction of the risk of disasters¹⁷. At the international level, this type of disaster includes situations of man-made or natural origin resulting from serious damage to people, property and the environment, without including armed conflicts and economic or political crises.

Hazardous industrial activities and prevention of environmental damage

As we have understood from the previous paragraphs, there are various treaties relating to industrial activities that regulate the related matter¹⁸, treaties that also protect parts of the

¹⁷COP, UNFCCC, Outcome of the work of the ad hoc working group on long-term cooperative action under the Convention, Decision CP.16, 2010, par. 14(e); COP, UNFCCC, Further guidance in relation to the adaptation communication, including, inter alia, as a component of Nationally Determined Contributions, referred to in Article 7, paragraphs 10 and 11, of the Paris Agreement, Decision 9/CMA.1, 15 December 2018, Preamble; United Nations Economic Commission for Europe (UNECE), Resilience to disasters for sustainable development, ECE/INF/NONE/2015/2/Rev.1, Geneva, 2019, p. 4; COP, Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change and disaster risk reduction, Decision XII/20, 2014.

¹⁸Convention on nuclear safety, adopted in Vienna on 17 June 1994, entered into force on 14 October 1996, with 78 states parties. Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, adopted in Helsinki on 17 March 1992, entered into force on 19 April 2000, with 41 states parties, art. 2. Annex I; Directive 2012/18/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 July 2012 on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances, amending and subsequently repealing Council Directive 96/82/EC Text with EEA relevance, OJ L 197, 24.7.2012, Annex I; Basel convention on the control of transboundary movements of hazardous wastes and their disposal, adopted in Basel on 22 March 1989, entered into force on 5 May 1992, with 189 states parties.

environment¹⁹ as well as others that have to do with the management of the risks of dangerous activities (Etemire, 2023)²⁰. These tools are universal in scope and apply the measures for accepted dangerous industrial activities at regional and sub-regional level.

Within this context the ILC in the project “Articles on the prevention of cross-border harm” has considered as dangerous those activities which derive from a materia risk of cross-border harm²¹. According to art. 2 of the project states consider as transboundary damage:

“(...) any damage to human health, property and the environment of another state which is measurable on the basis of objective criteria (...)”²².

Without naming dangerous activities based on objective criteria, thus identifying rules and principles that are also applicable to activities that do not involve any risk that cannot be dangerous due to their exposure to natural disasters²³. They also include

19United Nations Convention on the law of the sea (UNCLOS), adopted in Montego Bay on 10 December 1982, entered into force on 16 November 1994, with 168 states parties.

20See Aarhus Convention, op. cit.; Regional agreement on access to information, public participation and justice in environmental matters in Latin America and the Caribbean (Escazú Agreement), adopted in Escazú on 4 March 2018, entered into force on 22 April 2021, with 12 states parties; Convention on environmental impact assessment in a transboundary context (EIA Convention), adopted in Espoo on 25 February 1992, entered into force on 10 September 1997, with 45 states parties.

21 ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 1, comm. 2.

22Art. 2, comm. 4, which is affirmed that: “(...) the harm must lead to a real detrimental effect on matters such as, for example, human health, industry, property, environment or agriculture in other states. Such detrimental effects must be susceptible of being measured by factual and objective standards (...)”.

23Art. 1, comm. 15, which is affirmed that: “(...) it is possible that an activity which in its inception did not involve any risk (...) might come to do so as a result of some event or development. For example, a perfectly safe reservoir may become

some hazards that involve the use of certain substances beyond a certain threshold²⁴. These instruments specify the quantities and types of dangerous substances and also indicate the internal legal order of the Contracting States. Activities that use toxic and flammable substances and activities that can cause explosions or other accidents are dangerous (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018). Of course there is no shortage of tools that include activities considered by their own nature such as for example the extraction of oil, the manufacture of chemical products, the disposal of waste, the production of energy, etc.²⁵. Such assets arise from the type of operations involving its own size.

Other treaties identify the activities that states have the obligation to regulate to prevent environmental damage. Within this context, the UNCLOS of 1982 is taken into consideration, which provides measures for marine pollution caused by the

dangerous as a result of an earthquake, in which case the continued operation of the reservoir would be an activity involving risk (...)"

²⁴Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 1(b); Convention concerning the prevention of major industrial accidents (ILO Convention), adopted in Geneva on 22 June 1993, entered into force on January 3, 1997, with 18 states party, art. 3(b); Directive 2012/18/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on the control of major-accident hazards involving dangerous substances (Seveso III Directive), 4 July 2012, art. 3, par. 2.

²⁵Convention on environmental impact assessment in a transboundary context (EIA Convention), adopted in Espoo on 25 February 1992, entered into force on 10 September 1997, with 45 states parties. Directive 2011/92/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on the assessment of the impact of certain public and private projects on the environment (EIA Directive), 13 December 2011, as amended by Directive 2014/52/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council, 16 April 2014.

release of toxic or harmful substances that come from terrestrial sources, by the transit of ships, by extraction and exploration of seabed activities and by activities deriving risks of accidents which jeopardize the healthiness of sea waters²⁶. This type of activity takes into consideration the international norms and standards established by the UNCLOS and other treaties which have as their objective the protection of the marine environment by contributing to the activities that constitute a relative danger to the sea. International instruments that identify in detail the activities considered dangerous for the marine environment²⁷.

We have clearly understood that in international environmental protection law there is no shared definition for dangerous industrial activities and for activities deriving from situations of environmental pollution, fire accidents and explosions that cause negative hazards to human health and the environment in its complex.

Principle of precaution, environmental damage and obligation to protect

The Declaration adopted in 1972 by the “Conference of States on Human Environment” tried to specify some “rules” in

²⁶UNCLOS, op. cit., art. 194, par. 3.

²⁷Convention for the protection of the marine environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR Convention), adopted in Paris on 22 September 1992, entered into force on 29 March 1998, with 16 states parties, art. 2, par. 2(a).

relation to accidents causing damage to the territory, stating that:

“(...) responsibility to ensure that activities within their jurisdiction or control do not cause damage to the environment of other states (...)”²⁸.

A position that we later encountered on the Declaration of the Rio Conference on the Environment and Development of 1992²⁹ which recognized the international customary nature (Cote, 2011; Cogan, 2016; Mccaffrey, 2019; Voigt, 2019)³⁰. The mandatory objective of environmental prevention of a transboundary nature has resulted in dangerous activities which are foreseen by various treaties which include obligations of cooperation, information and consultation between the parties (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018). Other treaties also impose on states measures for the prevention of environmental damage³¹ thus recognizing environmental protection as such (Singh, 1987). These tools are inspired by the sustainable development goals and address the related economic development needs of environmental protection (Sands, 1999) producing procedural effects (Okowa, 1997).

²⁸Declaration of the United Nations conference on human environment (Declaration of Stockholm), Report of the United Nations conference on human environment, A/CONF.48/14/Rev.1, Stockholm, 1972, Principle 21.

²⁹Declaration of Rio, Principle 2.

³⁰ICJ, Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay (Argentina v. Uruguay), 2006-2010, par. 101. Permanent Court of arbitration, Iron Rhine arbitration (Belgium v. Netherlands), sentence of 24 May 2005, par. 59. ICJ, Certain activities carried out by Nicaragua in the border Area (Costa Rica v. Nicaragua), sentence of 16 December 2015, par. 104: “(...) to fulfill its obligation to exercise due diligence in preventing significant transboundary environmental harm, a state must, before embarking on an activity having the potential adversely to affect the environment of another state, ascertain if there is a risk of significant transboundary harm, which would trigger the requirement to carry out an environmental impact assessment (...)”.

³¹Aarhus Convention, op. cit., Escazú Agreement, op. cit.

The application of the prevention obligation includes the reduction of the risk of environmental damage³². This reveals mandatory prevention objectives and in the case of serious environmental damage there is a tendency to recognize the application of a risk precautionary approach by states which are required to act preventively despite the fact that it is the activity that causes negative effects for the environment (Boisson De Chazournes, 2010)³³. The precaution differs from the traditional prevention of environmental damage where the obligation to act preventively arises only when there is scientific certainty of a damage to the environment that is produced (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018). The precaution emerges in international environmental law by taking into consideration the seriousness of the environmental damages that are produced by economic development and the relative consequences on human life, thus making the regulation of the risks indispensable to provide the relative certainties to materialization (Boisson De Chazournes, 2010). Within this context we recall the Vienna Convention treaty for the protection of the ozone layer that was concluded in 1985³⁴ and other concluded and inspired treaties in the precautionary matter such as the United Nations Framework

32ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 1.

33Declaration of Rio, Principle 15.

34Vienna convention for the protection of the ozone layer, adopted in Vienna on 22 March 1985, entered into force on 22 September 1988, with 198 states parties.

Convention for Climate Change³⁵ and the conventions relating to biodiversity³⁶. However, it is not clear whether the precautionary principle has had the nature of a customary international standard and whether the related standards have a practical nature. The risk is based on the obligation of preventive action which sometimes ends up blocking the economic development of states.

Thus the main precautionary consequences are explained on the procedural level and involve an obligation relating to the risks of serious and irreversible environmental damage in the decision-making processes when it comes to future and uncertain risks. International courts are cautious and called to rule on the existence of an international law as well as to identify the risks of environmental damage (Islam, 2021)³⁷. Already in the advisory opinion of 2011 of the Chamber of the International

³⁵United Nations Convention on climate change (UNFCCC), adopted on 9 May 1992 in New York, entered into force on 21 March 1994, with 194 states parties, art. 3, par. 3.

³⁶Convention on Biological Diversity, adopted in Rio de Janeiro on 5 June 1992, entered into force on 29 December 1993, with 193 states parties, Preamble, art. 2. Cartagena protocol on biosafety-Convention on biological safety, adopted in Montreal on May 16, 2000, entered into force on 11 September 2003, with 173 states parties, art. 10, par. 6.

³⁷ICJ, Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay (Argentina v. Uruguay), op. cit., par. 135: “(...) a trend towards making [precautionary] approach part of customary international law (...)”. WTO Appellate Body, European Communities-Measures affecting the approval and marketing of Biotech products, WT/DS291/R, WT/DS292/R, WT/DS293/R, 29 September 2006, para. 7.88-7.89, which is affirmed that: “(...) there remain questions regarding the precise definition and content of the precautionary principle (...) since the legal status of the precautionary principle remains unsettled (...) we consider that prudence suggests that we not attempt to resolve this complex issue, particularly if it is not necessary to do so (...)”.

Tribunal of the Law of the Sea it was stated that:

“(...) the state that promotes prospecting and exploration activities has the obligation to adopt a precautionary approach as an integral part of the general obligation of due diligence of sponsoring state (...)” (Plakokefalos, 2012)³⁸.

We can understand that from the practice of international treaties and instruments on the subject of the environment and of the domestic law of states³⁹ it is considered that the obligation to prevent environmental damage tends to require the relative application of the precaution as a risk of damage that is serious and irreversible.

The obligation to prevent damage to the environment causes dangerous activities and is a general obligation that enters the principle of the due diligence as a minimum pre-established element by international courts as well as by treaties, international instruments on the matter, etc.⁴⁰

Regulation of dangerous industrial activities as an obligation deriving from a legal and administrative apparatus.

³⁸ITLOS, Advisory opinion on responsibilities and obligations in the Area, (Request for Advisory opinion submitted to the seabed disputes Chamber) List of cases: No. 17 Advisory opinion of 1st February 2011, par. 121- 122, 125-127, 131. https://www.itlos.org/fileadmin/itlos/documents/cases/case_no_17/17_adv_op_01021_1_en.pdf

³⁹Inter American Court, The environment and human rights, consultive opinion, OC-23/17, par. 176-177, 179. par. 178.

⁴⁰ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 3, comm. 7. ITLOS, Advisory opinion on responsibilities and obligations in the Area, op. cit., par. 117.

Mandatory prevention of environmental damage and industrial hazards

Prevent and everything that includes this notion from a legal point of view enters the ambit of the general obligation of the states which prepares for a legislative and administrative apparatus which seeks to protect environmental damage. This obligation was also affirmed by the Rio Declaration on the environment and development⁴¹ recognizing not only the customary nature but also the prevention of transboundary environmental damage⁴².

The obligation of the institutional apparatus for an effective protection of the environment has been incorporated in the treaties that regulate dangerous industrial activities⁴³. International instruments that identify the minimum requirements for the institutional apparatus adequately protect the environment from the effects of industrial activities. States must guarantee the activity that considers the environment dangerously. This depends on the granting of a permit by state authorities⁴⁴. States are required to be aware of the dangerous

⁴¹Declaration of Rio, Principle 11.

⁴²ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 3, comm. 4.

⁴³Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 3, par. 4. Convention on nuclear safety, op. cit., artt. 4, 7. UNCLOS, op. cit., artt. 207-208, 210-211; Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 4.

⁴⁴Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, cit., Annex IV; Convention on nuclear safety, cit., art. 7, par. 2; UNCLOS, op. cit., artt. 151, par. 2(a); 210, par. 3; Allegato 3, art. 2; OSPAR Convention, cit., Annex I, artt. 1-2.

activities that carry out the necessary preventive measures underlining that the ILC has established the obligation to authorize activities that cause damage in their own territory and in other states with a fundamental principle of international law⁴⁵. The institutional apparatus provides some rules for the safety of industrial plants to be active⁴⁶. These are safety measures that reduce the probability of accidents such as leakage of toxic substances, fires, explosions, etc.⁴⁷. The measures for damages caused by the exercise of industrial activities are attributed to the choices that are placed in the industrial plants. These types of tools try to identify the relevant criteria until the positioning of industrial activities is adequate to prevent and reduce the risks of accidents. Within this statement we note the EU Directive on accidents caused by the use of dangerous substances, which provides for specific prevention obligations in relation to those establishments which, due to their geographical position and their proximity to other industrial plants pose a higher risk of an accident⁴⁸. It requires Member States to take industrial accident risks into account in their development plans⁴⁹ and to ensure that there is a certain

⁴⁵ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 6, comm.1.

⁴⁶Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, cit., Annex IV; Convention on nuclear safety, op. cit., art. 7, par. 2; Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 4.

⁴⁷ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 16, comm. 1.

⁴⁸Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 9.

⁴⁹Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 13, par. 1.

distance between industrial establishments and residential areas⁵⁰. These measures are also envisaged by the Convention for the prevention of industrial accidents⁵¹ and adopted within the framework of the International Labor Organization (ILO). International instruments require the responsible authorities to ensure the implementation of the rules on damages deriving from industrial activities⁵². They are carried out through periodic inspections⁵³. These are tools that include detailed provisions relating to the methods that guarantee the subjects who enforce the legislation on the safety of industrial activities⁵⁴.

(Follows). Identification of obligations and risk assessment

The assessment of the impact on the environment and on dangerous activities has developed in the context of international environmental law. The International Court of Justice (ICJ) and the International Tribunal for the Law of the

⁵⁰Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 13, par. 2.

⁵¹Convention ILO, cit., art. 17. Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 7 and Annex V; Convention on nuclear safety, op. cit., art. 17.

⁵²Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 6, par. 1; Convention on nuclear safety, op. cit., art. 8, par. 1; Convention ILO, cit., art. 7.

⁵³Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 5, par. 2 and art. 20; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., Annex IV; Convention on nuclear safety, op. cit., art. 7, par. 2 and art. 14; Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 7, 8, 18; OSPAR Convention, op. cit., Annex I, art. 2.

⁵⁴Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 5, par. 1; art. 8, par. 1; art. 10, par. 1; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 3, par. 3 e art. 6, par. 2; Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 10-12.

Sea (ITLOS) have in practice recognized industrial activities resulting from damage to the environment from other states, as well as the obligation of each state to realize after a prior Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) what type of activity it may have⁵⁵. This type of measure establishes the risks for the environment deriving from carrying out dangerous activities. The results of the environmental impact assessment help states to decide on the precautionary measures they must take to avoid damage to the environment (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018). The environmental impact assessment procedure starts an activity dangerous for the environment which recognizes the minimum measure as an essential principle for states to be able to fulfill their obligation to prevent environmental damage⁵⁶. Elements that have entered into various treaties (Sands, Peel,

55ICJ, Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay (Argentina v. Uruguay), op. cit., par. 204. ITLOS, Advisory opinion on responsibilities and obligations in the Area, op. cit., par. 122. ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 7.

56ICJ, Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay (Argentina v. Uruguay), op. cit., par. 204: “(...) it may now be considered a requirement under general international law to undertake an environmental impact assessment where there is a risk that the proposed industrial activity may have a significant adverse impact in a transboundary context, in particular, on a shared resource. Moreover, due diligence, and the duty of vigilance and prevention which it implies, would not be considered to have been exercised, if a party planning works liable to affect the regime of the river or the quality of its waters did not undertake an environmental impact assessment on the potential effects of such works (...)”. ICJ, Certain activities carried out by Nicaragua in the border Area (Costa Rica v. Nicaragua), op. cit., par. 104: “(...) to fulfill its obligation to exercise due diligence in preventing significant transboundary environmental harm, a state must, before embarking on an activity having the potential adversely to affect the environment of another state, ascertain if there is a risk of significant transboundary harm, which would trigger the requirement to carry out an environmental impact assessment (...)”. ITLOS, Advisory opinion on responsibilities and obligations in the Area, op. cit., par. 149

Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018)⁵⁷ and into international instruments⁵⁸ in relation to the matter of environmental protection.

The jurisprudence and most of the treaties recognize the obligation to assess the environmental impact but do not identify the requirements that this procedure must have⁵⁹. The basis of the provisions are the sources of the pact type, other relevant international instruments, as well as what the Chamber of the International Tribunal of the Law of the Sea affirmed in its opinion of 2011⁶⁰. Where it is possible to identify a more precise content of the environmental impact assessment procedure, the states are required to identify the activities from which these risks may derive. It follows that from the obligation to assess the environmental impact derives a prior obligation to become aware of the activities that may pose a risk to the environment. By the way, the ICJ has stated that the state has an obligation to ascertain if there is a risk of significant transboundary harm,

⁵⁷EIA Convention, op. cit.; Directive EIA, op. cit. UNCLOS, op. cit., art. 206; Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 9. Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 4 and Annex III; Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 6 par. 2 and Annex I.

⁵⁸Declaration of Rio, art. 17; UNEP, Goals and principles of environmental impact assessment, UNEP/GC/Dec./14/25, 1987.

⁵⁹Pulp Mills on the River Uruguay (Argentina v. Uruguay), op. cit., par. 104: “(...) it is for each state to determine in its domestic legislation or in the authorization process for the project, the specific content of the environmental impact assessment (...)”. ICJ, Certain activities carried out by Nicaragua in the border Area (Costa Rica v. Nicaragua), op. cit., par. 104: “(...) determination of the content of the environmental impact assessment should be made in light of the specific circumstances of each case (...)”. ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 7, comm. 5.

⁶⁰ITLOS, Advisory opinion on responsibilities and obligations in the Area, op. cit., par. 149.

which would trigger the requirement to carry out an environmental impact assessment⁶¹. The obligation of environmental assessment was also taken into consideration in the Draft of articles on the prevention of transboundary environmental damage, according to which:

“(...) the obligation of prevention extends to taking appropriate measures identifying activities which involve such a risk (...)”⁶².

This obligation is also contained in various treaties concerning the prevention of environmental damage⁶³, which sometimes indicate the specific measures that states must adopt to identify the activities from which risks to the environment may arise. The managers of industrial establishments should periodically provide the public authorities with information on the risks posed by the industrial activity⁶⁴. The ILO Convention on the Prevention of Industrial Accidents contains a requirement to draw up a list of activities from which accidents can result and to update it regularly⁶⁵. Finally, the Aarhus Convention establishes a general obligation for states to possess information on the state of the environment⁶⁶.

⁶¹ICJ, *Certain activities carried out by Nicaragua in the border Area* (Costa Rica v. Nicaragua), op. cit., par. 104.

⁶²ILC, *Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm*, op. cit., art. 3, comm. 5.

⁶³Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 7, par. 1; Convention ILO, cit., art. 5; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 4, par. 1 and Annex IV; UNCLOS, op. cit., art. 204; OSPAR Convention, op. cit., art. 6 and Annex IV; Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 5, par. 1; Escazú Agreement, op. cit., art. 6.

⁶⁴Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 7, par. 1.

⁶⁵Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 5.

⁶⁶Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 5, par. 1. Escazú Agreement, op. cit., art. 6.

It is found that an activity constitutes a risk to the environment where the state carries out an environmental impact assessment concerning the activities that must be authorized towards a trend that recognizes the duration of the activities performance (Thouvenin, 1997; Meadows, 1998, Liakopoulos, 2020)⁶⁷.

Other indications that come from the IEA and the Goals and Principles of Environmental Impact Assessment were adopted by the UN Program for the protection of the environment⁶⁸. It has no legal force and the principles set out therein reflect the minimum requirements that the procedure should have, in the light of the internal and international practice of the states (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018). The Inter-American Court of Human Rights⁶⁹ also made reference to the minimum requirements. By virtue of the UNEP guidelines, the EIA should contain a description of the activity to be carried out and of the environment that could be affected; the information necessary to evaluate the possible risks for the environment; a description of the possible alternatives to the implementation of the project; a forecast of the long-term impact that the activity could have on the environment; information on mitigation measures for possible damage and on scientific uncertainties relating to the

⁶⁷ICJ, Project Gabčíkovo Nagymaros (Hungary/Slovakia), judgment, 25 September 1997, ICJ Reports 1997, pp. 88ss. Convention on nuclear safety, cit., art. 14; EIA Convention, op. cit., Annex V.

⁶⁸UNEP, Goals and principles of environmental impact assessment, op. cit.

⁶⁹Inter American Court, The environment and human rights, consultive opinion, op. cit., par. 150.

effects of the activity. The final act of the EIA should also explain in a summary manner and in non-technical language the results that emerged from the completion of the procedure⁷⁰. We can say that the same path has been followed and identified by international instruments such as the Convention on environmental impact assessment in a transboundary context⁷¹ and the European Union Directive on environmental impact assessment⁷². The vulnerability to natural events are always extreme and take into account the establishment objectives of the environmental impact assessment that must be carried out⁷³.

Already, ITLOS Chamber in its opinion of 2011 has considered:

“(...) for the purposes of determining the EIA requirements some instruments concerning the regulation of specific substances dangerous for the sea as they contain detailed guidelines on the information that the environmental impact assessment should provide”⁷⁴.

An environmental impact assessment implies that states must take into account the information acquired through the procedure in deciding whether to carry out the dangerous activity. When the risk turns out to be too high, the state will be required not to authorize the activity or to block it. The state

⁷⁰UNEP, Goals and principles of environmental impact assessment, op. cit., Principle 4.

⁷¹Directive EIA, op. cit., Annex II.

⁷²Directive EIA, op. cit., art. 2 par. 1 and art. 3.

⁷³Annex III, par. 1(f) which is affirmed that: “(...) the characteristics of the projects must be taken into account, taking into account in particular: the risks of serious accidents and/or disasters related to the project in question, including those due to climate change, based on scientific knowledge (...)”.

⁷⁴ITLOS, Advisory opinion on responsibilities and obligations in the Area, op. cit., par. 149. UNEP, Goals and principles of environmental impact assessment, op. cit., Principles 7 and 8; EIA Convention, op. cit., art. 3, par. 8; Directive EIA, op. cit., art. 6, par. 5.

may also decide to allow it by adopting precautions in order to establish whether a state has complied with the obligation of environmental impact assessment, i.e. determining a risk threshold deemed acceptable. In this way the public is required to participate in the environmental impact assessment procedure. This measure allows individuals who may be affected by the negative effects of the industrial activity to express their concerns and interests with respect to the project and to contribute to the decision regarding the authorization of the activity⁷⁵. Of course, the choice of the state to authorize the dangerous activity depends on the level of environmental protection that must be guaranteed. There are treaties that recognize the level of environmental protection and provide for the application of a precautionary approach to the risks of environmental damage (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018). The obligation to evaluate the risks according to the plans and programs that may derive from damage to the environment is fulfilled with the procedure that allows the integration of the risks resulting from the evaluation of the final decision. So we talk about strategic environmental assessment⁷⁶.

⁷⁵ITLOS, Advisory opinion on responsibilities and obligations in the Area, op. cit., par. 150.

⁷⁶Directive 2001/42/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 June 2001 on the assessment of the effects of certain plans and programmes on the environment, OJ L 197, 21 July 2001. Protocol on strategic environmental assessment to the convention on environmental impact assessment in a transboundary context, adopted in Kiev on 21 May 2003, entered into force on 11 July 2010, with 33 states parties.

(Follows). Disclosure obligations

In order to talk about environmental risks, it is first necessary the interested states to collect the relative information that has to do with dangerous activities and make it available. The information obligation in environmental treaties contributes to the achievement of the objectives in a plurality of forms (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018). Most environmental treaties require information-based reports to assess the level of treaty implementation. The related information concerns the measures that are adopted by the state to achieve the objectives of the treaty, the environmental damage, the dangerous activities that are authorized, etc. The function of the obligation to submit reports based on information is a criterion that is also included in the COP, i.e. the Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents where it asked states to provide information regarding the nature and location of dangerous activities in order to improve the understanding of the specific disaster risks and to prepare for them, in accordance with (“Understanding disaster risk”) the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction 2015-2030⁷⁷.

⁷⁷COP Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, Updated draft decision on strengthening the implementation of the Convention, ECE/CP.TEIA/2020/L.2, 20 November 2020, par. 10: “(...) serious disruption of the functioning of a community or a society at any scale due to hazardous events

Information also means the obligation to carry out activities that can have negative cross-border effects and can damage natural resources shared by several states. The information obligation is functional and also allows consultation between the various states involved, reaching a solution that guarantees a fair balance between the opposing interests. This obligation provides for some international instruments⁷⁸ and has also been recognized in rulings by international courts and national tribunals⁷⁹. Information means distinction of notification of the emergency situation in one's own territory resulting in a risk of serious harm of a cross-border nature. This obligation is also envisaged by various treaties which contain relevant provisions for the regulation of dangerous activities⁸⁰. Its purpose is to put the states whose territory is in danger in the conditions to prepare for the response and to mitigate the impact of the emergency. The importance of the obligation to notify came to the fore in connection with the Chernobyl nuclear accident. The

interacting with conditions of exposure, vulnerability and capacity, leading to one or more of the following: human, material, economic and environmental losses and impacts (...)”.

⁷⁸UNEP, Draft principles of conduct for the guidance of states in the conservation and harmonious exploitation of natural resources shared by two or more states, UNEP/GC/101, 1977, Principle 7; ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, cit., art. 8; Convention on the law of the non-navigational uses of international watercourses, op. cit., art. 11.

⁷⁹ Lake Lanoux Arbitration (French v. Spain), RIAA 281, 16 November 1957, par. 17. ICJ, Certain activities carried out by Nicaragua in the border Area (Costa Rica v. Nicaragua), op. cit., par. 108

⁸⁰UNCLOS, op. cit., art. 198; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 10; Convention on the law of the non-navigational uses of international watercourses, op. cit., art. 28, par. 2.

behavior of the Soviet Union in this case has, however, been criticized as it was considered to have delayed the dissemination of information on the risks of transboundary damage caused by the radioactive consequences of the accident (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018).

Particularly, the Chernobyl episode has led states to adopt the Convention and the related notification of nuclear accidents⁸¹ providing them with information on the nature, time and place of the event. In this case, the treaty leaves to the discretion of the state in whose territory the accident takes place the assessment of the danger of the event for the other states; therefore, in the event that it deems that the release of radioactive material does not produce negative cross-border consequences, it can decide not to notify the episode. However, a limitation of the Convention consists in the absence of provisions which require states to provide information on the risks of nuclear emergencies to their citizens⁸².

Other international instruments recognize the risks deriving from dangerous activities for individuals and distinguishing between them the obligation to guarantee access to information on risks from dangerous activities as well as the obligation to

⁸¹Convention on early notification of a nuclear accident, adopted in Vienna on 29 September 1986, entered into force on 27 October 1986, 127 states parties.

⁸²International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA), Guidelines on reportable events, integrated planning and information exchange in a transboundary release of radioactive materials, INFC1RC/321, 1985, par. 4.5.1.

provide information in the absence of a prior request⁸³. Access to information as well as the obligation to make it available to individuals require effective public participation in decision-making processes as a function of transparency of the procedures that lead national authorities to adopt decisions concerning the management of environmental risks⁸⁴. The risk of dangerous activities leads the national authorities to the relative decisions concerning the management of environmental risks, as well as the obligation of the possibility of asserting the responsibility of the states for choices regarding the environment⁸⁵. The information makes available and concerns the state of the environment in general⁸⁶, as well as the risks relating to dangerous activities already in underway⁸⁷ and those deriving from future industrial projects⁸⁸.

The obligation to guarantee access to information on the risks to the environment of dangerous activities is not absolute given that states are allowed to refuse to publish information that

83Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., artt. 4-5; Escazú Agreement, op. cit., art. 5; OSPAR Convention, op. cit., art. 9; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 15, par. 2; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., Annex VIII.

84Declaration of Rio, Principle 10; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 15, par. 3; ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 13, comm. 4; Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., Preamble.

85Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 4, par. 1; OSPAR Convention, op. cit., art. 9; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 15, par. 2; Escazú Agreement, op. cit., art. 5, par. 2.

86Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 2, par. 3; Escazú Agreement, op. cit., art. 2; OSPAR Convention, op. cit., art. 9.

87Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 14 and Annex V.

88Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 6, par. 2.

undermines particular needs of secrecy which are protected by domestic law, public security and national defence⁸⁹. Circumstances that states have the right to deny access to information on the environment and must be interpreted restrictively⁹⁰ justifying the reasons for the refusal⁹¹. States can make sure that individuals know that can have access to information⁹² and that this access is also guaranteed to the most vulnerable subjects⁹³. They must also facilitate the relative methods of access such as the obligations envisaged for the preparation of public registers and databases that contain information on the environment⁹⁴.

In finis, we can say that access to information concerning risks that aim to ensure the publicity of issues is different from those concerning risks posed by dangerous activities. The measures which may suffer the negative effects of an industrial activity

⁸⁹Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 4, par. 3; OSPAR Convention, op. cit., art. 9, par. 3; Escazú Agreement, op. cit., art. 5, par. 5; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 22.

⁹⁰Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 4, par. 3; Directive 2003/4/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 28 January 2003 on public access to environmental information and repealing Council Directive 90/313/EEC. OJ L 41, 14.2.2003, art. 4, par. 2; Convention of Escazú, cit., art. 5, par. 7.

⁹¹Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 4, par. 7; Escazú Agreement, op. cit., art. 5, par. 8; OSPAR Convention, op. cit., art. 9, par. 4.

⁹²Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 5, par. 2.

⁹³Escazú Agreement, op. cit., art. 5, par. 3.

⁹⁴Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 14; UNCLOS, op. cit., art. 205; Escazú Agreement, op. cit., art. 6, par. 4 and par. 7; Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 5, par. 2-7; Protocol on pollutant release and transfer registers to the Convention on access to information, public participation in decision-making and access to justice in environmental matters, adopted in Kiev on 21 May 2003, entered into force on 8 October 2009, with 38 states parties.

are different from those which are put in place to prevent and mitigate the damage⁹⁵. The beneficiaries of the information are those who are exposed to risks deriving from dangerous activities and who are informed of the risks of an accident⁹⁶, of the existing safety measures⁹⁷, as well as of the behavior relating to the emergency⁹⁸ and the ways in which a relative alarm will come⁹⁹. However, the information must be disseminated and in a way that is understandable to the recipients¹⁰⁰.

Decision-making processes involving public participation in dangerous industrial activities

Offering individuals the opportunity to express their opinions regarding choices that have an impact on the environment and

⁹⁵Escazù Agreement, op. cit., art. 6, par. 5; Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 5, par. 1(c). Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 14, par. 2; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 9; Convention on nuclear safety, op. cit., art. 16, par. 2; ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 13; Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 5, par. 1(c); EIA Convention, op. cit., art. 3, par. 8; Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 9. Escazù Agreement, op. cit., art. 6, par. 1 and par. 5. ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, art. 13, comm. 2.

⁹⁶Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 9, 20; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 14 and Annex V; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., Annex VIII.

⁹⁷Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 16; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., Annex V and art. 17; Convention on nuclear safety, op. cit., art. 16, par. 2.

⁹⁸Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 16; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., Annex V; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., Annex VIII.

⁹⁹Directive Seveso III, op. cit., Annex V; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., Annex VIII.

¹⁰⁰Directive Seveso III, op. cit., Annex V; Escazù Agreement, op. cit., art. 6, par. 6.

above all to final environmental decisions is presented as a measure that performs a dual function, namely that of increasing the legitimacy of decisions concerning the management of environmental risks by allowing national authorities to make decisions that reflect the relative level of risk accepted by society¹⁰¹, but also that of increasing the responsibility of states for choices regarding the environment. Thus states must indicate the relevance that the opinions expressed by individuals have on the final choice but also to grant them the opportunity to contest and/or review a final decision¹⁰².

The relevant treaties identify the minimum requirements that comply with the fulfillment of the obligation to guarantee public participation in decision-making processes concerning activities dangerous for the environment. The opinion of individuals on the choice of authorization of individual industrial projects are also the basis for reducing environmental damage and other types of accidents¹⁰³. Thus the treaties outline a relative obligation to listen to the interests affected by the decision on the start of the project¹⁰⁴. This approach was presented by the

101ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 13, comm. 10.

102Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 9; Escazù Agreement, op. cit., art. 8, par. 2; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 23(b).

103Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 6; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 15; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., Annex 7.

104Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 6; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 15; Directive EIA, op. cit., art. 9; EIA Convention, op. cit., art. 4, par. 2; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., Annex 7.

Escazù Agreement which speaks of a public right of participation¹⁰⁵ guaranteed as an authorization to start the activity and according to the options that are still in consideration¹⁰⁶. Participation is effective and must inform individuals who are interested in listening the decision-making procedure¹⁰⁷. This ensures access to the necessary information identifying the risks of the project for the evaluation of possible alternatives¹⁰⁸. This type of information takes into consideration a suitable time for the elaboration of the relative opinion¹⁰⁹. The modalities implemented are consultations remitted by the state¹¹⁰. After the adoption of the decision, those who are part of the decision-making process are disclosed, i.e. the reasoned decision indicating the public opinions gathered that influence the final choice¹¹¹.

These types of tools provide for public participation in decision-making processes and guarantee compliance with the definitions

¹⁰⁵Escazù Agreement, op. cit., art. 7: “Each party shall ensure the public’s right to participation”.

¹⁰⁶Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 15, par. 4; Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 6, par. 4; Escazù Agreement, cit., art. 7, par. 4.

¹⁰⁷Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 15, par. 2; Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 6, par. 2; Escazù Agreement, cit., art. 7, par. 6.

¹⁰⁸Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 15, par. 3; Convention of Aarhus, cit., art. 6, par. 6; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 9 par. 2 and Annex VIII.

¹⁰⁹Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 6, par. 3; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 15, par. 3; Escazù Agreement, op. cit., art. 7, par. 5.

¹¹⁰Convention of Escazù, op. cit., art. 7, par. 7; Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 6, par. 7.

¹¹¹Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 15, par. 4; Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 6, par. 8 and 9; Escazù Agreement, op. cit., art. 7, par. 8.

of plans and programs concerning activities that may have an impact on the environment¹¹². Public opinion intervenes in the elaboration of plans and programs in an antecedent moment that respects the decision on the single project. We recalled the Convention of Aarhus, the Escazù Agreement which calls for public participation also in legislative and regulatory processes having an impact on the environment¹¹³.

(Follows). Mandatory emergency plans

Emergency plans that are caused by industrial activities are envisaged by a plurality of treaties and international instruments for environmental reasons¹¹⁴. Risk management related to dangerous activities that do not eliminate and/or try to prevent, mitigate the effects on people, goods and the environment is thus regulated. For dangerous activities, emergency plans are drawn up on industrial plants¹¹⁵. For each plan, those responsible

¹¹²Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 7; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 15, par. 6; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 9, par. 2.

¹¹³Convention of Aarhus, op. cit., art. 8: “(...) each party shall strive to promote effective public participation (...) during the preparation by public authorities of executive regulations and other generally applicable legally binding rules (...)”.

¹¹⁴ILC, Draft articles on prevention of transboundary harm, op. cit., art. 16; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 12; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 8; Convention ILO, op. cit., artt. 9 and 15; Convention on nuclear safety, op. cit., art. 16; UNCLOS, op. cit., art. 199.

¹¹⁵Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 12, par. 1; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 8, par. 1 and 2; Convention ILO, op. cit., artt. 9 and 10.

for activating the emergency measures are designated¹¹⁶. Each plan must include the relative information for the safety measures, the behavior that the subjects in danger must adopt as well as to indicate the individuals and the authorities responsible for emergency management. The plans must determine the widespread modalities for the alarm, the necessary evacuation¹¹⁷ and all those provisions necessary for the situation before the accident¹¹⁸. The emergency plans update the changes undergone by the activity of the technical advances¹¹⁹. States can draw up emergency plans as a consultation to individuals and other states exposed to risks inherent in industrial activity (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018).

Protection of biodiversity and related international obligations

Biodiversity, which includes the variety of living organisms and ecosystems, provides important resources that can be used for

¹¹⁶Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 12, par. 1; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., Annex VII; Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 9 and 15.

¹¹⁷Directive Seveso III, op. cit., Annex IV; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., Annex VII; Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 9(d) and art. 16.

¹¹⁸Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., Annex VII, par. 6; Directive Seveso III, op. cit., art. 12, par. 3(d).

¹¹⁹Directive Seveso, op. cit., art. 12, par. 6; Convention on the transboundary effects of industrial accidents, op. cit., art. 8, par. 4; Convention ILO, op. cit., art. 9(d) and art. 15.

food, industrial or pharmaceutical purposes recognized as having a certain ethical and cultural value (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018). With the continuous reduction of biodiversity, one of the main causes is the over exploitation of natural resources, climate change, the spread of species and pollution¹²⁰. There are factors of a social, political and/or, economic nature that threaten biological diversity, i.e. the reasons why international instruments deal with the conservation of biodiversity and detect the prevention of disasters. Environmental damage affects natural disasters, a component of biodiversity which is particularly serious¹²¹. The risks of natural disasters affect an ecosystem which jeopardizes the functions¹²², i.e. the obligations to conserve biodiversity, and those to act preventively against these risks¹²³. Ecosystems perform functions of prevention of natural disaster risks and in the examples of wetlands¹²⁴ the forests that prevent the related risks from floods and landslides contribute to the mitigation of

120Millenium ecosystem assessment, Ecosystems and human well-being, 2005, p. 47: <https://www.millenniumassessment.org/documents/document.356.aspx.pdf>

121ICJ, Certain activities carried out by Nicaragua in the border Area (Costa Rica v. Nicaragua), op. cit., par. 155: “(...) the presence of Ramsar protected sites heightens the risk of significant damage because it denotes that the receiving environment is particularly sensitive (...)”; United Nations Forum on Forests, Report on 16^o session, E/2021/42-E/CN.18/2021/8, 2021, p. 19.

122Convention for the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, adopted in Paris on 16 November 1972, entered into force on 17 December 1975, with 194 states parties, art. 11, par. 4.

123COP Convention of Ramsar, The impact of natural disasters, particularly drought, on wetland ecosystems, Resolution VIII.35, 2002.

124COP Convention of Ramsar, Wetlands and disaster risk reduction, Resolution XII.13, 2015, par. 5.

climate change thanks to their carbon dioxide absorption capacities (Faivre, Sgobbi, Happaerts, Raynal, Schmidt, 2018). The Convention on Biological Diversity notes a plurality of activities that clarify the relative risks posed by genetically modified organisms, to the equitable access and benefits that are provided by biological resources¹²⁵.

The Ramsar Convention on Wetlands includes obligations to a specific ecosystem that retains a role in mitigating the effects of natural events such as floods and erosion of soils¹²⁶. These provisions contain treaties on the law of the sea and focus on the prevention of pollution¹²⁷. The ecosystem for ecological functions plays an important role for the variety of organisms found in forests as international instruments that lack binding legal force¹²⁸. The Convention against Desertification¹²⁹ also has

¹²⁵Nagoya protocol on access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilization to the Convention on biological diversity, adopted in Nagoya on 29 October 2010, entered into force on 12 October 2014, with 133 states parties.

¹²⁶World Conservation Monitoring Centre, *Global biodiversity: earth's living resources in the 21st century*, 2000.

¹²⁷UNCLOS, op. cit., artt. 116-120 e 194, par. 5; OSPAR Convention, op. cit., Annex V; Convention for the protection, management and development of the marine and coastal environment of the Eastern African Region, adopted in Nairobi on 21 June 1985, entered into force on 30 May 1996, art. 10. Convention for the protection of the marine environment and the coastal region of the Mediterranean, adopted in Barcelona on 16 February 1976, entered into force in 1978, amended in 1995, with 22 states parties, art. 10.

¹²⁸See the Declaration on forests and land use, adopted in occasion of the 26th COP of UNFCCC, 12 November 2021: <https://ukcop26.org/glasgow-leaders-declaration-on-forests-and-land-use/>.

¹²⁹United Nations Convention to combat desertification, adopted in Paris on 14 October 1994, entered into force on 26 December 1996, with 197 states parties, articles 3(d), 6.

the objective of soil degradation and the mitigation of negative effects¹³⁰. The regulations concerning this phenomenon also address the problem of biodiversity loss as a result of the impoverishment of the land and its own desertification (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018). Biological diversity is composed of a series of treaties that regulate the protection of particular species of plants and animals, the international trade of protected species as well as chemical products dangerous for ecosystems (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018).

Conservation and use of biodiversity. International obligations

The guarantee of sustainable use¹³¹ for the conservation of biodiversity has to do with the precautionary principle where preventive measures and a materialization prejudice are adopted for the loss and reduction of biodiversity¹³². The conservation obligations and the related sustainable use include the obligation to guarantee equitable access to the benefits deriving from

¹³⁰World Resources Institute, World resources (1992-3), 1992, p. 113.

¹³¹Convention of Ramsar, op. cit., art. 3; OSPAR Convention, op. cit., art. 2, par. 1(a) and Annex V, art. 2, which is affirmed that: "(...) the use of components of biological diversity in a way and at a rate that does not lead to the long-term decline of biological diversity, thereby maintaining its potential to meet the needs and aspirations of present and future generations (...)"

¹³²OSPAR Convention, op. cit., Annex V, art. 3(b)(ii); Convention on Biological Diversity, adopted in Rio de Janeiro on 5 June 1992, entered into force on 29 December 1993, with 193 states parties, Preamble, art. 1, par. 1.

biological diversity¹³³.

There are protection obligations that respect the areas that carry out a high risk of extinction. The objectives of disaster prevention state that the obligations of biodiversity protection reduce the risks of disasters from the effects of extreme natural events and pollution as well as the integrity of ecosystems¹³⁴. In the field of biodiversity protection, the concept of “ecosystem approach” developed following the emergence of it, according to which ecosystems should be conserved in order to maintain the essential services they provide to society¹³⁵.

Protected areas, protection of endangered species and designation obligations

So far we have noted some protective measures taken by the Convention on Biological Diversity. However, it did not include an identifying list of the components of biological diversity, acting on the objectives of conservation and sustainable use as a

¹³³Convention on Biological Diversity, op. cit., art. 1; Nagoya Protocol on access to genetic resources and the fair and equitable sharing of benefits arising from their utilization to the Convention on biological diversity, adopted in Nagoya on October 29, 2010, entered into force on 12 October 2014, with 133 states parties.

¹³⁴Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change, 2018, op. cit., Annex, par. 2.

¹³⁵Convention on Biological Diversity, Ecosystem approach, Decision V/6, 2000, Annex A, par. 1, affirms that: “(...) a strategy for the integrated management of land, water and living resources that promotes conservation and sustainable use in an equitable way (...)”.

vigilant and demanding even more sustainable measures for activities and processes for the danger of biodiversity¹³⁶. The identification criteria of the components of biological diversity are based on the protection of the ecosystem and/or habitat that host species with social, economic, cultural or scientific significance as well as species of particular rarity. The species of plants and animals that require special protection measures are those that risk extinction and those that have a use in the medical, agricultural, economic or scientific fields. The acts adopted by the Convention also recognize the importance of conserving those components of biodiversity necessary to ensure that ecosystems continue to fulfill their ecological functions¹³⁷. It also requires the establishment of protected areas or areas where special measures need to be taken to conserve biological diversity¹³⁸ such as those areas geographically defined which (are) designated or regulated and managed to achieve specific conservation objectives¹³⁹.

136Convention on international trade in endangered species of wild fauna and flora, adopted in Washington on 3 March 1973, entered into force on 1 July 1975, with 182 states parties, Annexes: I-III; Convention on the conservation of migratory species of wild animals, adopted in Bonn on 23 June 1979, entered into force on 1 November 1983, with 124 states parties, Appendices I and II; Ramsar Convention, cit., art. 2; Convention for the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, adopted in Paris on 16 November 1972, entered into force on 17 December 1975, with 194 states parties, art. 11, par. 4.

137COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change and disaster risk reduction, 2014, op. cit. COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change, Decision X/33, 2010; COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change, Decision XIII/4, 2016.

138Convention on biological diversity, op. cit., art. 8.

139Convention on biological diversity, op. cit., art. 2.

Protected areas that make available the obligation of conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity are obliged by the Convention to carry out environmental impact assessments of projects that can cause significant damage to biodiversity, as well as to take into consideration the risks related to the maintenance of biological diversity in the decision-making processes concerning the definition of policies and development plans¹⁴⁰. The Ramsar Convention states that it designates at least one wetland to be included in the treaty's list of wetlands of international significance¹⁴¹. It limits itself to saying that to establish whether a wetland has the requisites to be included in the list, one must look at its relevance from an ecological, botanical, zoological and hydrological point of view¹⁴². The criteria for determining this relevance are those of the ecosystem's ability to control and prevent floods as well as regulate the climate based on the area's ability to absorb carbon dioxide¹⁴³. The functions of wetlands have assumed particular importance with the worsening of the risks associated with the phenomenon of climate change. The inclusion of a wetland in

140Convention on biological diversity, op. cit., art. 14, par. 1.

141Convention of Ramsar, op. cit., art. 2, par. 1.

142Convention of Ramsar, op. cit., art. 2, par. 2.

143COP Convention of Ramsar, Strategic Framework and guidelines for the future development of the List of Wetlands of International Importance of the Convention on Wetlands (Ramsar, Iran, 1971)-2012 revision, Resolution XI.8, 2012, Annex 2, pp. 29-30; COP Convention of Ramsar, Guidance on identifying peatlands as Wetlands of International Importance (Ramsar Sites) for global climate change regulation as an additional argument to existing Ramsar criteria, Decision XIII.12, 2018, Annex I par. 4(d) e 11(c).

the list entails the obligation to promote its conservation and rational use (wise use)¹⁴⁴, while the maintenance of their ecological character, achieved through ecosystem approaches, within the context of sustainable development¹⁴⁵. The obligation to promote the conservation of wetlands that are not included in the list through nature reserves is immediately noticeable¹⁴⁶. The Convention for the protection of world heritage includes a list of cultural and natural sites considered to be of “outstanding universal value”, i.e. habitats of endangered species as well as natural areas of important value due to their aesthetic characteristics, their scientific value and risks of extinction¹⁴⁷. It is nothing more than a subsidiary list that includes cultural and natural sites of international importance threatened by “serious and specific dangers”, i.e. by large industrial projects, urbanization, fires, earthquakes, landslides, volcanic eruptions, sea level changes and floods, which require special measures for their maintenance. The inclusion of a site in the World Heritage List also facilitates international cooperation for its conservation. The state in whose territory the site is located can

¹⁴⁴Convention of Ramsar, op. cit., art. 3, par. 1.

¹⁴⁵COP Convention of Ramsar, A conceptual framework for the wise use of wetlands and the maintenance of their ecological character, Resolution IX.1, 2005, Annex A.

¹⁴⁶Convention of Ramsar, op. cit., art. 4, par. 1.

¹⁴⁷Convention for the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, adopted in Paris on 16 November 1972, entered into force on 17 December 1975, with 194 states parties, art. 11, par. 2

send a request for assistance to the World Heritage Committee¹⁴⁸ which is required to take it into consideration and decide on the opportunity and methods of providing any aid¹⁴⁹.

The related legal instruments are limited to identifying the internal measures that states must adopt for the conservation and sustainable use as components of protected biodiversity. From these documents emerges the tendency to recognize the concept of disaster risk reduction as an objective of biodiversity protection, an approach to risk that implies the adoption of measures aimed at reducing the vulnerability of biodiversity by respecting natural and technological hazards¹⁵⁰. The ultimate goal is measures for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity as a concept of ecosystem approach¹⁵¹.

Within this contest there are also conventions which give the COPs the definition of the species which apply the particular protection measures¹⁵². We recall for example the Convention on

148Convention for the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, adopted in Paris on 16 November 1972, entered into force on 17 December 1975, with 194 states parties, art. 11, par. 8.

149Convention for the Protection of the World Cultural and Natural Heritage, adopted in Paris on 16 November 1972, op. cit.

150Cultural Heritage Committee, Strategy for reducing risks from disasters at World Heritage properties, 2006, par. 34 e ss.

151COP Convention of Ramsar, Wetlands and disaster risk reduction, 2015, op. cit.; COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change and disaster risk reduction, 2014, op. cit; COP Convention of Ramsar, Climate change and wetlands: implications for the Ramsar Convention on Wetlands, Resolution XI.14, 2012, par. 26.

152Convention on international trade in endangered species of wild fauna and flora, op. cit., art. XI, par. 3(b)(c)(e); Convention on the conservation of migratory species of wild animals, adopted in Bonn on 23 June 1979, entered into force on 1 November 1983, with 124 states parties, Appendices I and II; art. XI, par. 1, 4 and 6.

International Trade for Endangered Species which contains limits and prohibitions on international trade based on the indicated world heritage lists. The Convention on Migratory Species requires states to conserve migratory species and habitats that are included in the general protection system of eliminating or reducing obstacles to their migration.

The ecosystem approach

The ecosystem approach is a main framework of action to achieve the objectives of the Convention by recommending states to integrate their national plans¹⁵³. This type of approach includes a management that integrates the different components of biodiversity taking into consideration the function of the ecosystem in which it is inserted. The ecosystem approach aims to ensure the maintenance and restoration of the services offered by ecosystems essential for human life and well-being. Very interesting is the mitigation of extreme natural effects and the response to climate change. States must give priority to the conservation of biodiversity components of the services they depend on¹⁵⁴. The benefits from ecosystems is an objective that the Convention on Biological Diversity pursues on a strategic

¹⁵³COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Ecosystem approach, Decision V/6, 2000.

¹⁵⁴COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Ecosystem approach, Decision V/6, 2000, Annex B, Principle 5.

level for the decade 2011-2020¹⁵⁵. However, the efforts made are not sufficient to achieve this type of objective¹⁵⁶ and above all the ecosystem approach which has been integrated into various biodiversity conservation strategies¹⁵⁷. On the other hand, the Ramsar Convention specified the rational use of wetlands and requires the maintenance of the services offered by the adoption of the ecosystem approach¹⁵⁸. It is an effective strategy for

¹⁵⁵COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Strategic plan for biodiversity 2011-2020, Decision X/2, 2010, Annex, par. 12.

¹⁵⁶COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Updated assessment of progress towards selected Aichi biodiversity targets and options to accelerate progress, Decision 14/1, 2018.

¹⁵⁷National environmental protection agency, Government of the Islamic Republic of Afghanistan, 6° National report to the Convention on biological diversity, 2019: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/nr/nr-06/af-nr-06-en.pdf>, p. 78; Ministry of tourism and environment, Government of the Republic of Albania, 6° National report to the Convention on biological diversity, 2019: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/nr/nr-06/al-nr-06-en.pdf>, p. 65; Government of Belgium, 6° National report to the Convention on biological diversity, 2019: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/nr/nr-06/be-nr-06-en.pdf>, p. 9; Ministère de l'environnement et développement durable, Gouvernement de la République démocratique du Congo, 6° rapport à la Convention sur la diversité biologique, 2019: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/nr/nr-06/cd-nr-06-fr.pdf>, p. 75; Government of Brazil, 6° National report to the Convention on biological diversity, 2019: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/nr/nr-06/br-nr-06-en.pdf>, pp. 87, 91, 189; Biodiversity working group for the Meeting of environment ministers, Government of Australia, Australia's national biodiversity strategy and action plan, 2021: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/au/au-nbsap-v3-en.pdf>, p. 12; Conservation and environment protection authority, Government of Papua Nuova Guinea, National biodiversity strategy action plan 2019-2024, 2019: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/pg/pg-nbsap-v2-en.pdf>, p. 11; Department of environment, Government of Fiji, National biodiversity strategy and action plan 2020-2025, 2020: <https://www.cbd.int/doc/world/fj/fj-nbsap-v2-en.pdf>, p. 30.

¹⁵⁸COP Convention of Ramsar, A conceptual framework for the wise use of wetlands, 2005, op. cit., Annex A. see the Declaration of the first joint ministerial meeting of the Helsinki and OSPAR Commissions, 2003, Annex 8: <https://helcom.fi/wp-content/uploads/2019/10/First-Joint-Ministerial-Meeting-of-the-Helsinki-and-OSPAR-Commissions.pdf>; UNESCO World heritage centre, Natural heritage strategy, 2006: <https://whc.unesco.org/uploads/activities/documents/activity-398-1.pdf>, p. 6.

conserving and using biodiversity, contributing thus to increasing the relevance of the issue of biological diversity in state policies. A sector that recognizes the prevention of disasters and the fight against climate change according to some ecosystems that perform functions of mitigating the impact of natural events.

The Convention on Biological Diversity¹⁵⁹, the Ramsar Convention¹⁶⁰, the World Heritage Committee¹⁶¹ and the UNEP Forum have put an argument in communis, i.e. acts that have recognized that climate change and extreme natural events pose a danger to ecosystems. Ecosystems provide critical services for climate change response and disaster risk reduction as an ecosystem makes an indispensable contribution to reducing the vulnerability of societies and the environment to disasters and climate change¹⁶². The COP of the Convention on Biological Diversity in 2019 adopted some integration guidelines based on the will of the national plans for biodiversity¹⁶³, where the

¹⁵⁹Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change, 2010, op. cit.; COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change, Decision XII/20, 2016. COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change and disaster risk reduction, 2014 COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change, 2018.

¹⁶⁰COP Convention of Ramsar, Wetlands and disaster risk reduction, 2015, cit.; COP Convention of Ramsar, Guidance on identifying peatlands as Ramsar Sites for global climate change regulation, 2018, op. cit.

¹⁶¹World Heritage Committee, Strategy for reducing risks from disasters at World Heritage properties, 2006, op. cit.

¹⁶²COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change, 2018, op. cit., Annex, par. 5. COP Convention of Ramsar, Wetlands and disaster risk reduction, 2015, op. cit., par. 17.

¹⁶³COP Convention on Biological Diversity, Biodiversity and climate change,

effectiveness of the ecosystem-based approach for the reduction of the risk of disasters and for the fight against climate change has been recognized by the international instruments that deal specifically with these two areas, namely the Hyogo framework¹⁶⁴ and the Sendai framework¹⁶⁵ which invite states to apply this approach. The Paris Agreement on climate change recalls in its preamble the importance of conserving ecosystems that absorb carbon dioxide and considers the conservation of ecosystems as an area in which cooperation between states should be developed in order to reduce losses caused by climate change (Knox, 2020)¹⁶⁶. These tools have affirmed the effectiveness of the ecosystem approach, prompting some states to develop various national strategies for the conservation and sustainable use of biodiversity that integrate this type of approach¹⁶⁷.

2018, op. cit.

¹⁶⁴Hyogo framework, par. 19(a)(b)(c).

¹⁶⁵Sendai framework, par. 28(d) e 30(n).

¹⁶⁶Paris Agreement-United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change, adopted in Paris on 22 April 2015, entered into force on 4 November 2016, with 189 states parties, art. 8. COP UNFCCC, The Glasgow climate pact, 2021: <https://ukcop26.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/11/COP26-Presidency-Outcomes-The-Climate-Pact.pdf>, p. 11.

¹⁶⁷See, Ministère de l'environnement, Gouvernement de la République de Haïti, Haïti biodiversité 2030 Stratégie nationale et plan d'actions pour la diversité biologique (révisé-2030), 2020, pp. 119-122, which is affirmed that: "(...) la gestion durable des écosystèmes est, d'ailleurs, de plus en plus considérée depuis Hyogo comme une approche efficace pour mettre en oeuvre les priorités en matière de Réduction de Risques de Catastrophes et d'Adaptation aux Changements Climatiques (...)"; Government of Papua Nuova Guinea, National biodiversity strategy, 2019, p. 63; Government of Fiji, National biodiversity strategy and action plan 2020-2025, 2020, cit., p. 32.

The obligation to mitigate

The UNFCCC has required states to adopt the relevant national plans to mitigate climate change by reducing greenhouse gas emissions as well as maintaining natural resources capable of capturing these gases¹⁶⁸. The objective of the mitigation was to stabilize the concentration levels of greenhouse gases and to prevent dangerous anthropogenic interferences with the climate system. One of the consequences of this interference consists in the increase of adverse natural events (McDonald, Telesetsky, 2018). The provision of specific mitigation obligations for developed countries is inspired by the principles of equity and “common but differentiated responsibilities” subject to complete discretion. The national contribution must be determined by each state in such a way as to represent progress over the previous one and to reflect its highest possible ambition, reflecting its common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities. For the purposes of determining the national contribution, each state notes the general provision contained in the preamble of the Paris Agreement according to which, in order to tackle the phenomenon of climate change, it should

168UNFCCC, op. cit., art. 4, par. 2(a).

“respect, promote and consider their respective obligations on human rights, the right to health, the rights of indigenous peoples, local communities, migrants, children, persons with disabilities and people in vulnerable situations and the right to development, as well as gender equality, empowerment of women and intergenerational equity” (McDonald, Telesetsky, 2018).

Contributions made at the national level are reported to the Conference every five years. This body provides an inventory of the emissions that come from human activities and the related information that is necessary to allow the evaluation of progress regarding the reduction of emissions as a fight against climate change, allowing the body to exert pressure on the states so that an implementation of the conventional provisions is adequate.

One of the mitigation objectives is the adaptation to the prevention causes where climate change as a current evolving phenomenon is visible from the forecasts of various sciences¹⁶⁹ and has the obligation of adaptation that prevents to mitigate the impact of climate change on societies. Thus the obligation to adapt pursues the objectives of imposing measures which aim to reduce the vulnerability of societies and the environment to climate change as a meaning of disaster risk of the notion of disaster risk reduction. The Framework Convention on Climate Change is limited to measures that promote adequate adaptation to climate change¹⁷⁰.

¹⁶⁹IPCC, Managing the risks of extreme events and disasters to advance climate change adaptation, Summary for policymakers, Special report, 2012, pp. 7-8.

¹⁷⁰UNFCCC, op. cit., art. 4, par. 1(b).

Mitigation has made adaptation efforts urgent (Sands, Peel, Fabra, MacKenzie, 2018). The Conference of 2010 held in Cancun underlined

“the need to increase the adaptive capacity of societies to the effects of climate change; to this end, a framework for action was adopted and a dedicated committee was set up to promote its implementation”¹⁷¹.

It was affirmed in the acts adopted by the 2010 COP and merged into the Paris Agreement. Adaptation is considered a complementary objective to mitigation and both are considered necessary to respond to the problem of climate change. It consists of

“enhancing adaptive capacity, strengthening resilience and reducing vulnerability to climate change, with a view to contributing to sustainable development”¹⁷².

The concepts of “capacity”, “resilience” and “vulnerability” are based on COP of 2010 instead the documents adopted by the IPCC¹⁷³ are presented as adaptation measures that focus on social and environmental factors due to climate change that causes catastrophic effects for societies. We're talking for an approach that risks posed by climate change are consistent with disaster risk reduction tools. These instruments have contributed to the Paris Agreement on adaptation. The Cancun COP¹⁷⁴ and

¹⁷¹COP UNFCCC, Report of the COP on its 16^o session, Addendum, Part two: Action taken by the COP at its 16^o session, FCCC/CP/2010/7/Add.1, Cancun, 2010, par. 14 and 20.

¹⁷²COP UNFCCC, Report of the COP on its 16^o session, Addendum, Part two: Action taken by the COP at its 16^o session, FCCC/CP/2010/7/Add.1, Cancun, op. cit.

¹⁷³IPCC, Managing the risks of extreme events and disasters to advance climate change adaptation, Full report, Special report, 2012, p. 37.

¹⁷⁴COP UNFCCC, Report of the COP on its 16^o session, Addendum, Part two, Cancun, 2010, op. cit., par. 14(e).

the IPCC report on adaptation¹⁷⁵ are inspired by the Hyogo framework as well as the decision taken by the Conference of the parties which included the Paris Agreement and the Sendai framework¹⁷⁶. From the communications presented to the Conference and in particular from article 7, par. 10, of the Paris Agreement, it emerges that the Sendai framework is a tool that has as its objective adaptation to climate change¹⁷⁷ and disaster risk reduction as a complementary objective with integrative

175IPCC, Managing the risks of extreme events, Full report, 2012, op. cit., p. 29.

176UNFCCC, Adoption of the Paris Agreement, FCCC/CP/2015/10/Add.1, 2015.

177Environmental protection agency, Government of Liberia, Liberia's First Adaptation Communication to the UNFCCC, 2021: https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/First_Adaptation_Communication_AdCom_LI_BERIA.pdf, p. 19; Government of Portugal, Portugal's adaptation communication to the UNFCCC, 2021: https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/2021%20Portugal%20ADCOM_UNFCCC.pdf, p. 33; Environmental protection environment, Government of Ghana, Ghana's adaptation communication to the UNFCCC, 2021: https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/Ghana_AdCom%20to%20the%20UNFCCC_November%202021_Final%20with%20foreword.pdf, p. 35; Government of Austria's adaptation communication to the UNFCCC, 2021: <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/Austria%27s%20Adaptation%20Communication%20on%20%2827.10.2021%20FINAL%29.pdf>, p. 26; Government of Australia, National Climate Resilience and Adaptation Strategy 2021-2025 Positioning Australia to better anticipate, manage and adapt to our changing climate, 2021: <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/National%20Climate%20Resilience%20and%20Adaptation%20Strategy%20-%20FINAL.pdf>, p. 29; Slovenia and European Commission on behalf of the EU and its Member States, Adaptation communication of the European Union, 2021: https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/20211007_EU_adaptation_comms.pdf, p. 17; Ministry of environment, forestry and tourism, Government of Namibia, First adaptation communication to the UNFCCC: <https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/namibia-adaptation-communication-to-the-unfccc.pdf>, par. 3.2.7; Portugal's adaptation communication, cit., pp. 6 e 25; Austria's adaptation communication, cit., p. 23; Australia's National Climate Resilience and Adaptation Strategy 2021-2025, cit., pp. 8 e 15; Adaptation communication of the European Union, pp. 3 e 11; Government of Japan, Adaptation communication pursuant to article 7, par. 10 of the Paris Agreement, 2021: https://unfccc.int/sites/default/files/resource/JAPAN_adaptation_communication.pdf, pp. 20-21.

purposes. The Paris Agreement and mitigation leaves the possibility for states to undertake this type of objective where adaptation measures are based on a participatory and transparent decision-making process that takes into consideration the size and needs of the ecosystems of vulnerable groups guided by science and traditional knowledge¹⁷⁸. Adaptation plans are included where the provision of climate change assessment procedures and vulnerabilities are determined by the individuals and ecosystems that respect the interventions as a priority¹⁷⁹.

Concluding remarks

Preventing disasters in international environmental law is now a concrete and precise matter as a result of the approaches contained in various international instruments with control functions on the implementation of treaties. Certain minimum measures are taken to fulfill disaster prevention obligations that impose obligations of an international nature. The disaster risks deriving from the exercise of dangerous industrial activities, as well as the conduct of states are considered to comply with the standards of diligence pertaining to the prevention of industrial disasters, where states manage industrial and technological risks, risk identification and assessment procedures which make

¹⁷⁸Paris Agreement, op. cit., art. 7, par. 5.

¹⁷⁹Paris Agreement, op. cit., art. 7, par. 5.

accessible and disseminate information on risks, guaranteeing decision-making processes and emergency plans, as well as the risk of damage to the environment which is serious and irreversible and where due diligence requires states to apply a precautionary approach.

The precaution is taken for the purposes of biodiversity conservation and the fight against climate change. The justification for applying the precautionary approach puts at risk the fact that it increases the probability and scale of natural disasters. The recognition of the connection between environmental degradation and natural disasters has required a series of rules, principles and/or, obligations of a general nature where the content is specified by the decisions and resolutions of the COP. The COPs recognized the contribution of biodiversity which has the objective of reducing the risk of disasters, thus elaborating the ecosystem-based disaster risk reduction and identifying the measures for the conservation of biodiversity as functions of reduction of the social environmental vulnerabilities of natural disasters. Through the Paris Agreement, the phenomenon of climate change contains obligations on the subject of climate change mitigation without excluding that these obligations take on a precise content due to the effects they have in the sector of the protection of human rights as well as the disaster risk reduction measures that prevent

soft law acts in the field of disaster risk reduction in the regulatory process, i.e. in Art. 7 of the Paris Agreement relating to the formulation of the provision implemented in the internal legal order of the states (Boyle, 2018).

References

Aronsson-Storrier, M. (2019). *Exploring the foundations: The principles of prevention, mitigation, and preparedness in international law. The Cambridge handbook of disaster risk reduction and international law*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 54ss.

Bartolini, G. (2017). A universal treaty for disasters? Remarks on the International Law Commission's Draft Articles on the protection of persons in the event of disasters. *International Review of the Red Cross*, 99 (3), 1105ss.

Boisson De Chazournes, L. (2009). Environmental treaties in time. *Environmental policy and law*, 39 (6), 298ss.

Boisson De Chazournes, L. (2010). *New technologies, the precautionary principle, and public participation. New technologies and human rights*. Oxford University Press, Oxford.

Boyle, A. (2018). Climate change, The Paris agreement and human rights. *The International and Comparative Law Quarterly*, 67(4), 760, 772ss.

Brown, R. (2021). Invoking international environmental norms through treaty interpretation. *The Law & Practice of International Courts and Tribunals*, 20(2), 239ss.

Cogan, J.K. (2016). Certain activities carried out by Nicaragua in the border area (Costa Rican v. Nicaragua) construction of a

road in Costa Rican along the San Juan River (Nicaragua v. Costa Rican). *American Journal of International Law*, 110 (2), 322ss.

Cote, S. (2011). Protesting pulp Argentina battles Pulp Mills on the river Uruguay. *Law and Business Review of the Americas*. 17 (4), 738ss.

Dzehtsiarou, K. (2015). *European consensus and the legitimacy of the European court of human rights*. Cambridge University press, Cambridge.

Etemire, U. (2023). The Escazú agreement: Public access to environmental information and the goal of a sustainable future. *Journal of Energy & Natural Resources Law*, 41 (1), 75ss.

Faivre, N., Sgobbi, A., Happaerts, S., Raynal, J., Schmidt, L. (2018). Translating the Sendai framework into action: The EU approach to ecosystem-based disaster risk reduction. *International Journal of Disaster Risk Reduction*, 32, 4-10

Islam, M.R. (2021). Overhaul of the SDT provisions in the WTO: Separating the eligible from the ineligible. *Pace International Law Review*, 34, 5ss.

Knox, J. (2020). The Paris agreement as a human rights treaty. In D., Akande, J., Kuosmanen, H., Mcdermott, D., Roster, D. (eds.). *Human rights and 21st century challenges: Poverty, conflict, and the environment*. Oxford University Press, Oxford, 334ss.

- Lauta, K.C. (2016). Human rights and “natural” disasters. In S.C. Breau, K.L.H. Samuel. *Research handbook on disasters and international law*. Edward Elgar, Cheltenham, 91-110.
- Liakopoulos, D. (2020). *The role of not party in the trial before the International Court of Justice*. ed. Maklu, Antwerp, Portland.
- Mccaffrey, S.M. (2019). *The law of international water courses*. Oxford University Press, Oxford
- McDonald, J., Telesetsky, A. (2018). Disaster by degrees: The implications of the IPCC 1.5°report for disaster law. *Yearbook of international disaster law, 1*, 184ss.
- Meadows, F. (1998). The first site visit by the International Court of Justice. *Leiden Journal of International Law, 11*, 604ss.
- Okowa, P.N., (1997). Procedural obligations in international environmental agreements. *The British Yearbook of International Law, 67 (1)*, 278ss.
- Peel, J., Fisher, D. (ed.) (2016). *The role of international environmental law in disaster risk reduction*. ed. Brill, Leiden
- Peters, A. (2017). The refinement of international law: From fragmentation to regime interaction and politicization. *International Journal of Constitutional Law, 15 (3)*, 675ss.
- Plakokefalos, I. (2012). Seabed Disputes Chamber of the International Tribunal for the Law of the Sea. *Journal of Environmental Law, 24 (1)*, 135ss.

Sands, P. (1999). International courts and the application of the concept of “sustainable development”. *Yearbook of United Nations Law*, 3, 389-405

Sands, P., Peel, J., Fabra, A., MacKenzie, R. (2018). *Principles of international environmental law*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 230ss.

Sefsaf, F. (2022). Protection of persons from disasters in international law. *International Review of Law*, 10(3).

Singh, K. (1987). Foreword. In R.D. Munro Chairman, J.G. Lammers. *Environmental protection and sustainable development. Legal Principles and Recommendations. Adopted by the Experts Group on Environmental Law of the World Commission on Environment and Development*. Trotman, Martinus Nijhoff, London, Dordrecht, Boston, xi-xii.

Thouvenin, J.M. (1997). La descente de la cour sur les lieux dans l'affaire relative au projet Gabčíkovo-Nagymaros. *Annuaire Français de Droit International*, 43, 334ss.

Tladi, D. (2017). The International Law Commission’s Draft Articles on the Protection of Persons in the Event of Disasters: Codification, progressive development or creation of law from thin air?. *Chinese Journal of International Law*, 16 (3), 429ss

Voigt, C. (2019). *International judicial practice on the environment. Questions of legitimacy*. Cambridge University Press, Cambridge

Wierserna, A. (2009). The new international law-makers? Conferences of the parties to multilateral environmental agreements. *Michigan Journal of International Law*, 31, 234-235.

Zorzi Giustiniani, F., Sommario, E., Casolari, F., Bartolini, G. (ed.). (2018). *Routledge handbook of human rights and disasters*. ed. Routledge, London & New York.